

1 **Coal mining wastes valorisation as raw geomaterials in**
2 **construction: A review with new perspectives**

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11 Abstract

12

13 Historically coal mining wastes have been viewed as heterogenous and hazard-prone
14 geomaterials. Given that failures of colliery tips and tailing dams are reported on a regular
15 basis, reclamation of coal mining wastes from storage facilities is increasingly being
16 considered. There is a resistance to the use of coal mining waste in construction industry despite
17 scattered but growing reports of successful applications. As the construction industry around
18 the globe seeks to reduce its carbon emissions by looking for supplements for cement, the
19 voluminous amount of coal mining wastes currently stored in spoil heaps and impoundment
20 facilities present a potential source of raw materials. This article reviews the literature on the
21 geochemical, geotechnical and structural engineering properties of coal mining waste
22 geomaterials to assess their suitability as replacement for both aggregates and binders in
23 concrete and cementitious composites (as opposed to reviewing the properties of those products
24 themselves). It is found that coal mining wastes are indeed good candidates (as raw materials)
25 for the uptake and process into higher level construction purposes. Geochemically, the key to
26 a successful upcycling operation is the knowledge of their mineral contents (which is typically
27 diverse and varies from one mine to another) and the processes they undergo while being
28 transformed into constituents of new materials. The few studies on concretes made with coal
29 mining wastes indicate that the mineralogical and mechanical characterisation of the wastes to
30 obtain a mix featuring strength and durability performance that meets specification is important
31 to a successful utilisation. In the geotechnical literature, coal mining wastes are known to be
32 highly heterogeneous and may host expandable minerals with potential durability problems.
33 However, this review also found that simple geotechnical index tests can be conducted to yield
34 useful information for the initial screening of coal mining wastes into a construction product.
35 The state-dependent properties of coal mining wastes (e.g., water retention, hydraulic
36 conductivity, shear strength) are found to be governed by complex factors such as coal content,
37 particle size and shape, pore size and shape, and the presence and interaction of pore air and
38 pore water in the void space, some of these are well-studied but much of these are to be further
39 researched.

40 List of abbreviations

41	ACMW	activated coal mine waste
42	AMD	acid mine drainage
43	ASR	alkali-silica reaction
44	CMWG	coal mining waste geomaterial
45	CU, CD	consolidated undrained, consolidated drained
46	FI	flakiness index
47	GSD	grain size distribution
48	HREE	heavy rare earth element
49	LCA	life cycle analysis
50	LL	liquid limit
51	LREE	light rare earth element
52	OPC	ordinary Portland cement
53	m-CU, m-CD	multistage consolidated undrained, multistage consolidated drained
54	PL	plastic limit
55	PSD	pore size distribution
56	REE	rare earth element
57	SCM	supplementary cementitious material
58	SI	shape index
59	UC, UU	unconfined compression, unconsolidated undrained
60	XRD	X-ray diffraction

61 List of symbols

62	χ	effective stress parameter
63	ψ	pressure head
64	τ	shear strength
65	φ, φ'	total friction angle, effective friction angle
66	σ, σ'	total stress, effective stress
67	c, c'	total cohesion, effective cohesion
68	C_u	coefficient of uniformity
69	D_{50}	grain size for 50% finer by weight
70	D_s	fractal dimension of a grain size distribution
71	D_{s1}, D_{s2}	fractal dimension of populations 1, 2, respectively
72	$d_s, d_{s \max}, d_{s \min}$	grain size, maximum grain size, minimum grain size
73	$d_{s \max 1}, d_{s \max 2}$	maximum grain size of populations 1, 2, respectively
74	$d_{s \min 1}, d_{s \min 2}$	minimum grain size of populations 1, 2, respectively
75	G_s	specific gravity
76	G_s_{CMWG}	specific gravity of coal mining waste geomaterial
77	G_s_{coal}, G_s_{others}	specific gravity of coal and of materials other than coal
78	e, e_{\max}, e_{\min}	void ratio, maximum void ratio, minimum void ratio
79	$f(\dots)$	function
80	$I_d, I_d(2)$	slake durability index, slake durability index of the second cycle
81	K, K_s	unsaturated hydraulic conductivity, saturated hydraulic conductivity
82	L	length
83	$M1, M2$	mass percentage of populations 1, 2, respectively
84	M_s	dry mass of particles
85	m_{coal}	coal content
86	q	flow rate
87	S_r	degree of saturation
88	s, s_e	matric suction, air entry/expulsion suction
89	u_a, u_w	pore air pressure, pore water pressure
90	z	length in vertical direction

91 1. Introduction

92 Coal mining waste geomaterials (CMWGs) consist of fragments of rocks and coal seams which
93 are brought to the surface during coal extraction processes (Skarżyńska 1995a). Historically
94 coal mining wastes have been viewed as problematic geomaterials. They are chemically
95 heterogenous, prone to particle breakage by compaction, rapid degradation by wetting-drying
96 cycles, and susceptible to liquefaction when loosely deposited. Furthermore, spontaneous
97 combustion and leaching of acidic water to the surrounding environment are among the
98 environmental challenges they present. These problems are associated with several special
99 properties of coal and coal-bearing geomaterials in the wastes.

100 Coal extraction is still ongoing, for example in 2019, the total coal production in Europe, North
101 America and Asia Pacific amounted to 577.4 million tonnes (Mt), 701.5 Mt, and 5,911.8 Mt
102 respectively (British Petroleum 2020). This ongoing production adds more CMWGs to the
103 amount already in storage facilities (> 10,700 Mt by some estimates (Fan et al. 2014; Frías et
104 al. 2012; Islam et al. 2021; National Research Council 2007; Skarżyńska 1995a; Zhao et al.
105 2008)), and imposes additional costs on producers and extra burdens on the environment. **Given**
106 **the concerning state of the global climate (Pierrehumbert 2019; IPCC 2021), the environmental**
107 **impacts of coal extraction and production activities are rapidly becoming a focus for**
108 **researchers in civil engineering.**

109 In order to address the major challenges presented by coal mining in Europe and throughout
110 the world, innovative concepts are being developed for managing, recycling and upcycling
111 waste geomaterials generated by coal mining activities. One potential solution is to upgrade
112 CMWGs as constituents of sustainable construction materials and products, and as such
113 contributing to the establishment of a circular economy concept in the coal mining areas. In
114 this respect there is a strong demand for geomaterials in the construction industry: for example
115 **5 tonnes (of natural aggregates) per capital** are produced in Europe for construction purposes

116 every year (European Aggregates Association 2017), meanwhile there is an imperative to
 117 conserve the natural resources (Torres et al. 2017). CMWGs have been utilised successfully in
 118 many low to medium level civil engineering applications such as controlled fills in mining
 119 zones, earthworks and land restoration, as rock armour in shoreline structures, aggregates in
 120 road construction and rail embankment (Hammond 1988; Skarżyńska 1995b). An enhanced
 121 understanding of the chemical and physical properties of CMWGs could accelerate their uptake
 122 and broaden their applications, particularly for higher level construction purposes. To meet this
 123 aim, the properties of CMWGs need to be determined accurately, with a focus on their
 124 characterisation for reuse. Furthermore, the relationships between different properties and how
 125 some of them may be more relevant than others in specific engineering applications are key to
 126 investigate, together with some operational aspects of reclaiming the wastes from storage
 127 facilities and **processing them into applications. The latter may necessarily include life cycle**
 128 **analysis (LCA) studies of the applications to reflect more fully connections between**
 129 **environmental impacts and resource utilisation. In this regard, it is noted that the currently**
 130 **available experimental data for CMWGs are too limited to allow for an adequate service life**
 131 **prediction, and important life cycle inventory data are lacking in the available LCA databases.**
 132 Previous investigations into the (primarily geotechnical) properties of coal waste stockpiles
 133 and tailing lagoons were mainly driven by concerns about the stability of these structures.
 134 Compiled databases (Golder Associates Ltd 2015; ICOLD 2001; Rana et al. 2021) show that
 135 mine waste deposits pose a significant instability risk globally. Major failures of colliery tips
 136 and tailing dams are reported on a regular basis (Bishop 1973; Santamarina et al. 2017), some
 137 of most notable ones are listed in Table 1.

138

139 **Table 1.** Some failures of CMWG deposits investigated and reported in the literature

Time and location	Description	Potential causes of failures	References
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21/10/1966, Aberfan, South Wales, UK	A flow slide involved approximately 107,000 m ³ of coal waste material.	The driving force of the failure was the buildup of pore water pressure at the toe of the tip, exacerbated by a loosely packed fabric of the fill making it susceptible to a flow liquefaction.	(Bishop et al. 1969)
26/02/1972, Logan County, West Virginia, USA	A flood involving approximately 498,000 m ³ of water was initiated by the failure of a coal waste embankment dam further upstream.	The upstream dam was made of coal spoils and its foundation consisted mostly of coal sludge. Piping in the foundation has probably led to excessive deformation and the subsequent overtopping of the dam.	(Davies et al. 1972)
1979-1991, Southwest Virginia, USA	11 slope failures in coal waste embankments required remediation.	Slaking and weathering of the embankment fill has probably reduced the shear strength to below what is required for stability. Failures were likely to have been initiated by the built-up of pore water pressure at the toe of the slopes.	(Donovan and Karfakis 2003)
2001-2002, Central Anatolia, Turkey	2 spoil pile instabilities involved more than 20 Mt of spoil material.	Gradual weathering and particle breakage by hauling, dumping and truck traffic have reduced the dominant grain size of the spoil material to silt-sized. Low residual strength was mobilised between the spoil and basal planar surface. Water pressure built-up from rainfall has initiated the instabilities.	(Kasmer et al. 2006)
Prior to 2004, Kalimantan, Indonesia	2 coal waste dump failures, the 1 st involved 80 Mm ³ and the 2 nd involved 10.5 Mm ³ of material	No cause of failure was stated, although it was emphasized that coal waste geomaterials were generally unsaturated, when water entered their pore space, they tended to slake, soften and weaken. A residual strength could have been developed along a thin layer, and the waste dumps could easily fail in a remolded mode.	(Pells 2016)
30/04/2004, South Field coal mine, Northern Greece	40 Mm ³ of dump materials was displaced up to 300 m from their original footprint, at a rate of 40-50 m/day.	The dump material was primarily low plasticity clays with local inclusions of silts and sand. The dump material has covered up a spring, choking its flow. Failure was possible due to a high-water pressure developing around the spring inside the spoil deposit.	(Steiakakis et al. 2009)
22/12/2008, Kingston Fossil Plant,	An uncontrolled release of 4.12 Mm ³ coal fly ash slurry was triggered	The embankment was built on a loosely-packed sluiced ash whose behaviour was contractive with a low undrained shear strength. Laboratory tests showed that the	(AECOM 2009), (TVA 2009)

Tennessee, USA	by the rupture of a coal ash lagoon embankment	peak undrained shear strength of the sluiced ash was reached at 0.5% strain. At a higher strain, the undrained strength rapidly decreased to as low as 4.8 kPa.	
31/10/2013, Alberta, Canada	A tailing pond embankment was breached, released 670,000 m ³ of coal waste water and 90,000 tonnes of fine particles into the Athabasca River	The embankment was overtopped due to a rise in the pond level prior to the full breach. Piping or retrogressive erosion of the upper loose material may have contributed to the initial overtop.	(HMTQ v. Prairie Mines & Royalty ULC 2017)
10/04/2020, Singrauli, India	400,000 tonnes of coal fly ash slurry were released from an impoundment facility, travelled a path of 6.5 km, spread an average width of 30m and an average depth of 1m.	The failure was triggered by an earthwork operator damaging a section of an embankment wall. However, the subsequent failure of the wall and the uncontrolled release of slurry was due to a severe hydrostatic pressure on the upstream of the embankment.	(Hiralal Bais v. Reliance Sasan Power Ltd. & Ors 2020)

140

141 There is a strong need to rehabilitate coal waste stockpiles and tailing lagoons due to their
142 instability risk. However, any significant reclamation activity of coal waste from existing
143 deposits should be carefully managed since reclamation of waste from a waste storage structure
144 can alter its hydro-mechanical balance. The response which is triggered is dependent on
145 mineralogical composition, particle and pore size distribution, fabric, water retention and
146 permeability of the materials. The fabrics of coal waste stockpiles and tailing lagoons are also
147 highly heterogeneous; the top few meters of a stockpile may be weathered while the materials
148 at depths can be relatively fresh. Coal tailings are often stratified into layers of distinct particle
149 sizes. Moreover, except those wastes buried permanently below the water table, most CMWGs
150 are unsaturated, yet there are few experimental researches in the literature characterizing the
151 unsaturated properties of CMWGs. The most recent studies (Fityus and Li 2006; Vidler et al.
152 2020) highlighted the importance of mineralogical composition, grain size distribution (GSD),
153 pore size distribution (PSD), weathering and fabric, water retention and permeability.
154 Characterising unsaturated properties of a CMWG is essential not only to understand its hydro-

155 mechanical behavior and its use as compacted fill in geotechnical applications (Alonso and
156 Cardoso 2010) but also for other foreseeable applications in the construction industry,
157 including their use as constituents in concrete and cement-based materials, replacing, e.g.,
158 natural aggregates. Considering the substantial contribution of the construction industry to CO₂
159 emissions and natural resource depletion, such applications could hit the dual targets of serving
160 the circular economy goals and minimising the adverse environmental impacts of both coal
161 mining and concrete production. As such, significant savings could be made in the demand and
162 use of natural raw materials for construction works, especially in areas near to active or
163 decommissioned mines.

164 In order to turn CMWGs into valuable resources, particularly for construction, “fit-for-
165 purpose” characterisations must be undertaken with regards to properties specific to their
166 intended applications. Such characterisations will be detailed in this review paper. These
167 properties include:

168

169 1. Hydro-chemical properties of repurposed CMWGs

170 A major concern associated with the reuse of CMWGs in the construction industry is the
171 degradation/reaction of some of their constituents when they make contact with the
172 hydrosphere (herein referred to as their hydro-chemical properties). This could potentially
173 include generation of acid from the oxidation of disposed sulfide minerals when exposed to
174 water or oxygen in the air (explained more fully in section 2.3.1), which would not only pose
175 an environmental hazard but also influence the durability of the materials and (geo)-structures
176 built using these materials. The determination of hydro-chemical properties of the repurposed
177 CMWGs is necessary to determine and quantify the effects of key mechanisms responsible for
178 ageing and degradation of the performance of repurposed CMWGs when exposed to various

179 environments (e.g., salty, anaerobic, acidic, extreme climatic, etc.), and to understand their
180 effects on the durability of the materials and products in which CMWGs may be incorporated.
181 The current state of understanding the CMWG’s hydrochemical properties is reviewed in
182 section 3 of the paper.

183

184 2. Geotechnical index properties and hydro-mechanical behaviour of repurposed CMWGs

185 In order to provide a sound basis for the application of recycled CMWGs, it is important to
186 evaluate their mechanical properties and to assess whether or not repurposed CMWGs can
187 perform as well as natural geomaterials in various proposed “upcycling” applications. There
188 are already clear evidences of recycled aggregates from the construction industry being used in
189 new constructions (Guthrie and Mallett 1995; Silva et al. 2014) and, as such, by far most of the
190 knowledge available in the literature is about the mechanical properties of recycled materials
191 from the construction industry itself. **c, also with reference to their potential influence on the
192 mechanical and durability performance of cement-based construction materials employing
193 them as “secondary” raw materials.**

194 The current state of understanding of CMWG’s geotechnical index properties and hydro-
195 mechanical behaviour is reviewed in section 4 of this paper. The focus will be on how some
196 mineralogical compositions of CMWGs may be captured in geotechnical index properties and
197 ultimately manifest in hydro-mechanical behaviours of CMWGs. It will be demonstrated, using
198 data from the literature and original data from this study, that a geotechnical laboratory
199 characterisation of CMWGs can be undertaken in a simple way, yet yield highly valuable
200 information for the initial screening of CMWGs in specific applications.

201

202 2. Coal production and coal mining wastes

203 2.1. Coal production

204 Coal is mined by both underground- and surface-mining methods. Typical coal production and
205 coal mining wastes are shown schematically in Figure 1. Depending on the amount and type
206 of the coal (brown or black coal) available in an area, processing sophistication would differ
207 hence producing different amounts and types of wastes (British Geological Survey 2010).
208 Latest estimates put the current annual global coal production at 8,129.4 Mt (British Petroleum
209 2020). The total global coal reserve is at 1.14 trillion tons (EIA 2020), which is sufficient to
210 last another 132 years at current rate of production.

211

212

213 **Figure 1:** Coal production and coal mining wastes (adapted from British Geological Survey
214 (2010), Coates and Yu (1977))

215

216 2.2. Coal mining wastes

217 Coal mining waste may be classified on the basis of its origin in a mine processing scheme:
218 aggregate wastes include overburden and coarse rejects separated from the coal, and washery
219 wastes comprise the finer fractions derived from the washing plant (Figure 2). Aggregate
220 wastes and coarser washery wastes are typically disposed in spoil heaps, and finer washery
221 wastes are disposed in slurry form in impoundment facilities. Figure 3 shows the coal mining
222 wastes in a spoil heap from Forjas Santa Barbara (FSB) mine in Spain. Although coal mining
223 wastes are increasingly being channeled into earthworks, roadworks, and are further processed
224 into innovative construction materials (e.g., eco-efficient cements, brick and concrete blocks),
225 there remains a significant amount generated by past and current mining operations that are
226 directly dumped in spoil heaps and/or waste storage facilities. For example, in China, which is
227 currently by far the world's single biggest producer and consumer of coal, about 36% of coal
228 mining wastes are not utilised (Li and Wang 2019). There is, of course, a vast amount of
229 historical coal mining wastes stored in spoil heaps and impoundments globally (> 6,600 Mt by
230 Gutt and Nixon's estimate (1979)), and > 10,700 Mt by more recent regional estimates (Fan et
231 al. 2014; Frías et al. 2012; Islam et al. 2021; National Research Council 2007; Skarżyńska
232 1995a; Zhao et al. 2008)).

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Figure 2: A classification of coal mining wastes (adapted from Skarżyńska (1995a)), d_s is grain size

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238

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Figure 3: Coal mining wastes in a spoil heap from Forjas Santa Barbara mine, Spain

240 Many CMWG deposits may be in metastable states. Past investigations (Table 1) show that
241 failures of colliery spoil heaps were significantly contributed by shear strength degradation due
242 to weathering, instability of a loosely packed fabric formed by dumping or poor compaction,
243 combined with adverse structural features and a triggering event. Failures of coal tailing and
244 ash ponds have been significantly contributed by their loosely packed fabric, unevenly placed
245 slurry pumping, combined with adverse structural features and a triggering factor such as
246 seismic excitation or heavy rainfall. Major failures of colliery tips and tailing dams (some with
247 catastrophic consequences) are reported on a regular basis (Bishop 1973; Santamarina et al.
248 2017). There is a clear need to increase the effort currently put towards rehabilitating these
249 CMWG deposits.

250

251 2.3. Hazards posed by coal mining waste

252 The high volume of residues generated by mining activities are usually put into storage
253 facilities; the characteristics of the storage/disposal site being of paramount importance in order
254 to handle the environmental hazards that may occur, as pointed out by Twardowska et al.
255 (2004). The coal waste aggregates are usually simply stockpiled by the mine, compacted as
256 fills or used in the base of tailings dam embankments (Figure 1). After a mine operation has
257 concluded, it is a common practice to refill the excavation with the generated solid wastes. The
258 environmental impacts of the mine will then depend mainly on how this stockpiled waste
259 subsequently interacts with the atmosphere, rainwater, and in particular, groundwater.

260 The most well documented environmental impact of stockpiled coal waste is the seepage of
261 acidic water: a phenomenon known as acid mine drainage (AMD). The acids generated may
262 contaminate the nearby water sources and thus must be treated following disposal. Indeed,
263 many aspects of stockpile design are intended to prevent/retard AMD, or capture the seepage
264 water so it can be treated. In the refining plant the coal is ground and mixed with water,

265 consequently generating a significant amount of slurry waste. On occasions, the contaminated
266 slurry has been disposed in rivers or the ocean, or piped into storage facilities or underground.
267 A common prevention strategy is to encapsulate wastes identified as potentially acid-
268 generating within those that are acid-neutralising (by virtue to their carbonate-bearing
269 mineralogy). The causes and effects of AMD are described in more detail in section 2.3.1.A,
270 whereas possible bi-product of AMD, the combustion of coal waste stockpiles, is described in
271 section 2.3.2.

272 A documentation of the major impacts produced by coal mining waste more generally has been
273 developed by Younger (2004), who identified the following five items: air pollution, fire
274 hazards, ground deformation, water pollution, and water re-source depletion. Disposal of coal
275 mining waste, like any proposal for its reuse as a secondary raw material for civil engineering
276 or construction, hence requires a robust understanding of the geochemical processes it is likely
277 to undergo. Together with the physical and mechanical properties of the waste, which are
278 summarized in section 4 of this paper, geochemical processes are explored in the reminder of
279 this section and in section 3.

280

281 2.3.1. Acid Mine Drainage

282 CMWGs often contain minerals that are chemically unstable in the presence of oxygen and
283 water, which may dissolve after prolonged exposure to rainwater/groundwater. The most
284 common such minerals are the sulfides (chiefly pyrite and pyrrhotite), and their dissolution can
285 substantially lower the pH of the contact water. This phenomenon is termed as acid mine
286 drainage (AMD), and is well documented at many coal mines around the world (INAP 2009).
287 AMD is a major environmental concern because in addition to the ecological hazard presented
288 by low pH, such acidic water has an enhanced capacity for dissolving toxic metals that are
289 frequently present as trace elements in coal, such as lead, arsenic, cadmium, selenium, copper

290 and zinc (Park et al. 2019). AMD therefore has the potential to widely disperse toxic metals,
291 contaminating major aquifers and watercourses far beyond the location of the source materials.
292 In the construction industry, the principal hazards posed by sulfide oxidation are the expansive
293 stresses generated within concrete when iron- and sulfate-bearing compounds such as
294 ferrihydrite or gypsum precipitate from acidified porewater (Chinchon et al. 1995).
295 Although there are many chemically reduced species that can contribute to AMDs, sulfide is
296 overwhelmingly the most common species found in CMWGs (INAP 2009). Among the sulfide-
297 bearing minerals pyrite (FeS_2) is the most abundant (Nordstrom 2011, Park et al. 2019), and its
298 net oxidation to yield sulfuric acid can be written as follows:

300 Whilst the expression in Eq. (1) usefully indicates the 1:2 molar ratio between the amount of
301 pyrite oxidized and the amount of acid ultimately generated, it does not describe the oxidation
302 process comprehensively. In particular, the oxidant in the reaction need not be molecular
303 oxygen, and at pH lower than around 3.5 ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) can assume this role if it is available:

305 This alternative oxidation pathway is often sustained by microorganisms which maintain the
306 supply of ferric iron by oxidizing ferrous ion (Fe^{2+}) (Crundwell 2003). A decrease in pH caused
307 by the oxygen-mediated reaction (the first equation above) can create the conditions necessary
308 for this alternative Fe^{3+} -driven process, which can proceed 2 to 3 orders of magnitude faster
309 (INAP 2009). The oxidation rate may however be reduced by the presence of neutralizing
310 materials such as calcite, which can maintain near-neutral pH if suitably distributed within the
311 waste. A further important influence on reaction rate is the surface area of the pyrite, which
312 can be orders of magnitude larger for intricate ‘framboidal’ growths than for the simpler
313 ‘euhedral’ crystals.

314 In summary, the rate of sulfide oxidation within a particular CMWG is a complex function of

315 the dissolved oxygen concentration and the pH of the contact water, the exposed surface area
316 of the sulfides, and the chemistry of the accompanying minerals.

317 2.3.2. Combustion

318 Although CMWGs are materials that have been rejected from the coal production process, this
319 does not preclude them from containing percentage-level concentrations (by mass) of
320 carbonaceous material. This coal can ignite if not stored or transported appropriately (Onifade
321 and Genc 2020). Spontaneous combustion is commonly observed at coal mines in coal spoils
322 (though less commonly in overburden materials) and is often initiated by sulfide oxidation (see
323 section 3.1.2.3), which is a strongly exothermic process. Spontaneous combustion at mine sites
324 is generally mitigated by limiting the thickness of waste dumps (to promote cooling),
325 constructing them in wind shadows where possible (to minimize headwind-assisted oxidation),
326 and placing lower limits on material grain-size. The application of CMWGs as aggregates will
327 require similar considerations, especially if the conditions envisaged are likely to permit sulfide
328 oxidation (e.g., continuous exposure to moist air).

329

330 3. Upgrading CMWGs as raw materials in construction industry

331 The mineralogy of CMWGs varies widely, since it depends on the mineralogy of the geological
332 formations overlying or adjacent to the coal seam being mined. Consequently, no single
333 shortlist of minerals can be said to comprise CMWGs exhaustively, although the range of
334 possibilities is restricted by the sedimentary origin of the coal, which typically requires the
335 adjacent ‘host’ formations to also be sedimentary. Exceptions include certain types of sediment
336 which contain fragments of ancient igneous rocks (‘breccias’), and mines at which some of the
337 rocks overlying the coal seam (the ‘overburden’) are not of sedimentary origin.

338 Consequently, CMWGs usually comprise of minerals found in the sedimentary rocks; minerals
339 that are rich in silicon and aluminum oxides, chemically stable at near-surface conditions, and

340 frequently hydrated. These include quartz, varieties of clay (e.g., kaolinite and illite), potassium
341 feldspar, micas, carbonates (calcite, dolomite), and less commonly sulfates, halides, iron oxides
342 and amphiboles. The nature of coal formation, which invariably comprises the accumulation
343 of plant matter in a stagnant, often water saturated environment, followed by diagenesis,
344 dictates that certain similar mineral transformations have been documented to occur across
345 different coal deposits world-wide. For example, coal seams of the Permian Shanxi formation
346 in Juye coalfield, China, are dominated by kaolinite and calcite, with claystone and sandstone
347 interburden dominated by kaolinite, montmorillonite, and illite; and quartz, chalcedony,
348 feldspar and kaolinite respectively (Zhang et al. 2019). These minerals are derived from
349 volcanic and granitic source rocks in the pre-diagenetic period which then underwent
350 weathering in a peat swamp environment; such acidic conditions are favourable for the
351 weathering of feldspar and formation of kaolinite (Zhang et al. 2019).

352 Besides these ‘major’ constituents, a wide range of minor constituents have been reported for
353 CMWGs. Again, such constituents can be highly variable, however, the nature of coal
354 formation, and its resultant physical and chemical properties dictate that certain minor
355 constituents commonly exist. For example, sulfide bearing minerals, such as pyrite and
356 chalcopyrite also form under oxygen-poor conditions and are therefore common in CMGWs.
357 Such minerals, in addition to coal, are typically reported as most relevant for CMWG reuse
358 potential due to their capacity to inhibit the geotechnical performance of CMWG-bearing
359 construction materials (Section 3.1.2). Another common constituent of coal-bearing strata is
360 the radioactive and ecotoxic element uranium. This co-association is due to the fact that carbon-
361 rich organic matter within the coal-bearing strata can act as a potent sorbent and reducing agent,
362 which when exposed to groundwater containing uranyl ions, can result in their selective
363 precipitation as solid (and surface bound) mineral phases. Such occurrences are widespread;
364 for example, Huang et al. (2012) undertook a literature survey of uranium occurrence in 1184

365 Chinese coal samples with a range typically within 0.5-10 mg/kg, and an average of
366 approximately 3 mg/kg.

367 Despite such common constituents the typically diverse mineralogy of CMWGs gives rise to a
368 similarly wide range of geotechnical and geochemical properties. As such, the suitability of
369 CMWGs for a particular construction application can vary from one mine to another. While
370 the presence of certain minerals is desirable for some applications (aggregates require hard
371 minerals like quartz for example), as mentioned earlier, the absence of others can be just as
372 important (such as sulfides in concrete additives). The effects of mineralogy on the main
373 applications of CMWGs are discussed in the following subsections, with a focus on chemical
374 processes than geotechnical properties (which are discussed in section 4).

375

376 3.1. Chemical properties necessary for use of CMWGs as raw 377 materials in construction industry

378 CMWGs have been investigated as a replacement for both aggregates and binders (cements) in
379 concrete and cementitious composites. The re-purposing as construction aggregates is
380 reasonably established for low-grade applications such as road-fills (Amrani et al. 2020),
381 reclamation fills (Indraratna et al. 1994; Rujikiatkamjorn et al. 2013), road/railway
382 embankments (Wilmoth and Scott 1979) and in various other applications where limited
383 amounts of Portland cement are used for stabilization and performance improvement (González
384 Cañibano 1995; Okagbue and Ochulor 2007).

385 Use as concrete aggregate is a significantly more lucrative application because the
386 specifications are more demanding; not only must the CMWG's constituent minerals have
387 sufficient strength to meet the geotechnical specifications to be employed as concrete
388 aggregates, but they must not undergo adverse chemical reactions with the cement (i.e., they
389 must be chemically stable). CMWGs have been used successfully to manufacture fine

390 aggregates for some low-spec concretes such as paving blocks (Rossi dos Santos et al., 2013),
391 whereby the waste fraction with relative density/specific gravity 2.4-2.8 was separated,
392 crushed, and substituted for the conventional aggregate (sand) in varying proportions.
393 Compressive strength and abrasion resistance tests indicated the maximum acceptable
394 substitution to be 50% by volume. Modarres et al. (2018) investigated the use of different types
395 of CMWGs, including powder, ash and aggregates, in roller compacted concrete for
396 pavements, in replacement percentages up to 20% by volume, demonstrating that in all cases
397 (but for the 20% powder replacement) the required specifications (about 28 MPa cube
398 compressive strength at 28 days) were successfully met. Best results, also in terms of
399 toughness, were obtained with relatively low replacement percentages (5% by volume),
400 irrespective of the CMWG type, with levels of performance comparable to that of the parent
401 mix, if not slightly better, due to the filler effects of the CMWGs. Higher replacement
402 percentages resulted in performance deteriorating.

403 Wang and Zhao (2015) produced a series of concretes using Chinese coal gangue as coarse and
404 fine aggregate to determine the influence of gangue grading on their geotechnical properties.
405 Fuller's curve n values ranged from 0.44 to 0.68, and 0.62 was identified as the optimal one,
406 resulting into a maximum 28-day compressive strength of the concrete equal to 37MPa. Li et
407 al. (2021) investigated the microstructural and geotechnical properties of concrete prepared
408 using a coal gangue as aggregate, dominantly composed of silica, kaolinite and calcium
409 carbonate. The concretes obtained were significantly weaker than those prepared using quartz
410 gravel as aggregate.

411

412 3.1.1. Pozzolanic activity

413 A desirable potential application for CMWGs is their utilization as a supplementary
414 cementitious material (SCM) in blended concrete. Such blends are increasing in popularity as

415 the construction industry seeks to reduce its carbon emissions by finding supplements for
416 cement, whose production is extremely energy and carbon intensive (4-5 GJ and ~800 kg
417 emission of CO₂ per ton of ordinary Portland cement (Shamir et al. 2020)). CMWGs are good
418 SCM candidates because they often contain large fractions of clay minerals that can be
419 conditioned to acquire pozzolanic properties. These clays, kaolinite in particular, must be
420 thermally activated by calcining between 500 and 900 °C for around 2 hours (Frías et al. 2012;
421 Vigil de la Villa et al. 2014), the precise conditions are somewhat varying for the different
422 CMWGs tested to date. This treatment dehydrates kaolinite to form metakaolin, a
423 semicrystalline compound whose pozzolanic activity arises from its propensity to react with
424 portlandite (Ca(OH)₂) in cement to form cementitious calcium silicates (Bich et al. 2009).
425 Mixtures of such thermally activated wastes with conventional cement, ground to particle sizes
426 of order ~75µm, have yielded concretes with properties comparable to those employing purely
427 conventional cement.

428 Much of the research into CMWGs as pozzolans to date has been conducted on Spanish waste
429 materials. Thermally activated CMWGs from Spain have been repeatedly used to replace
430 between 20% and 50% of ordinary Portland cement (OPC), yielding concretes with tensile
431 strengths and corrosion resistance comparable with those containing OPC exclusively. Such
432 products have been manufactured using both coal aggregate waste (Caneda-Martínez et al.
433 2019; García Giménez et al. 2016; Vigil de la Villa et al. 2014) and coal washery waste (Frías
434 et al. 2012; Rodríguez et al. 2021). For example, Frías et al. (2012) synthesized concrete blends
435 containing (individually) coal washery waste and coal aggregate waste as substitutes for up to
436 20% of the OPC. Their products were type II/A cement compliant with European standards
437 with respect to sulfate and chloride concentration, as well as meeting European setting time,
438 volume stability and strength requirements. Caneda-Martínez et al. (2019) found that the
439 corrosion resistance of rebar to chloride ions was improved by the substitution of 20% of the

440 OPC by thermally activated CMWGs. In general, these CMWG-blends require higher
441 water/cement ratios than conventional OPC, e.g., approximately 13% more in blends
442 employing 20% SCMs (Frías et al. 2012).

443 Similar results were obtained by Vegas et al. (2015) who studied the performance of blended
444 cements with CMWG replacements of up to 20%. Small to moderate replacement percentages
445 (6% to 10%) led to slight increase of compressive and flexural strength in the short term and a
446 moderate decrease in the longer term (> 90 days), whereas a slight decrease in strength (less
447 than 10%) was always observed for the highest investigated replacement percentage.
448 Significantly, drying shrinkage was also increased by the replacement of OPC with CMWGs.
449 This has been attributed to the following phenomena: CMWGs accelerating the hydration of
450 cement; pozzolanic reactions between the metakaolin contained in the CMWGs and calcium
451 hydroxide from the hydration of cement clinker; and lastly, to an increase in capillary pressure
452 that is a consequence of a change in the pore size distribution.

453 While studies on CMWGs to date have focused on metakaolin as the source of pozzolanic
454 activity, it is not necessarily the only such constituent in the waste media. Kaolinite
455 concentrations in the CMWGs investigated varies widely, from about 70% to as low as 14%
456 (Rodríguez et al. 2021), suggesting that kaolinite might not be the only constituent that yields
457 pozzolanic properties upon thermal activation. The possibility of alternatives is well
458 demonstrated with the success observed by employing coal fly ash as a pozzolanic replacement
459 (Jovanovic et al. 2014; Shamir et al. 2020), which mainly comprises aluminosilicate glass (the
460 first known pozzolans, sourced from southwest Italy, which were also glassy in nature) rather
461 than metakaolin or any other clay or clay derivative. Another alternative pozzolan synthesis
462 method has been demonstrated by Wang et al. (2021), who combined sodium hydroxide
463 solutions with various mixtures of coal gangue and blast-furnace slag to yield prototype road-

464 stabilization materials (a less demanding application, but nonetheless a legitimate example of
465 pozzolanic activity).

466 We venture here to suggest that thermal activation of CMWGs could remove their constituent
467 sulfides by oxidizing them directly to SO₂ gas and hematite. Hu et al. (2006) reviewed studies
468 of pyrite oxidation in air and reported that this decomposition reaction occurs at less than 800
469 K; a similar temperature to that employed for thermal activation of kaolinite. The possibility
470 that a single such thermal treatment (or some specially optimized variant) might both produce
471 pozzolans and suppress undesirable sulfide oxidation (see section 3.1.2.3) is worthy of further
472 investigation.

473

474 3.1.2. Chemical processes deleterious to use of CMWGs as construction 475 materials

476 *3.1.2.1. Alkali-Silica Reaction*

477 The presence of amorphous silica in concrete aggregate can cause swelling and spalling (Figure
478 4) if it reacts with hydroxide compounds within the cement; a phenomenon known as alkali-
479 silica reaction (ASR). The problematic reaction products are calcium silicate hydrate gels,
480 which are hygroscopic and generate large internal stresses if they absorb water from the
481 concrete pore solution (Fanijo et al. 2021). CMWGs may contain many varieties of amorphous
482 silica (such as chert or opal) or strained quartz (which is also vulnerable to ASR), since these
483 are also common in sedimentary rocks. Thorough petrographic inspection of CMWGs to search
484 for these amorphous phases is essential if they are to be used as concrete aggregates. Inspection
485 procedures appropriate for this task have been standardized (e.g., ASTM C1567-21, ASTM
486 C1260-21) which include experimental tests as well as petrographic examination. It should be
487 noted that to the authors knowledge, to date, ASR has not been reported in concretes prepared
488 using CMWGs as aggregate. Since this application remains relatively untested, and since ASR

489 is a chronic condition that can take years to develop, little can be inferred about the propensity
490 for CMWGs in general to promote this reaction. Interestingly, the use of SCMs, including coal
491 fly ash, has been reported to mitigate damages from ASR (e.g., Shafaatian et al. 2013), although
492 the mechanism responsible is not known with certainty. Indeed, the mitigation of ASR has
493 become a motivation for using SCMs, underlining the interdependence of the different
494 chemical processes described in this review.

495

496

497 **Figure 4:** A highway barrier deformed by alkali-silica reaction (ASR) (Akhnoukh 2013).
498

499 *3.1.2.2. Alkali-Carbonate Reaction*

500 The alkali-carbonate reaction (ACR) is a deformation-inducing chemical process analogous to
501 the ASR, in which carbonates rather than amorphous silica reacts with hydroxide from the
502 cement to form a hygroscopic gel. The degree to which carbonate decomposition (known as
503 dedolomitization) is responsible for deformation is uncertain however, since carbonates are
504 popular concrete aggregates and yet most do not exhibit ACR (Aquino et al. 2010). For
505 example, Katayama (2009) and Grattan-Bellew et al. (2010) have suggested that some cases of
506 ACR are actually instances of ASR, where the role played by the carbonates is to contribute
507 amorphous silica (silicious dolomites are common geological materials); the dedolomitization

508 itself being merely incidental. Since calcite and dolomite are both common constituents of
509 CMWGs, the presence, abundance, and chemistry of these minerals should be carefully
510 determined in any CMWG before it is considered as a concrete aggregate.

511

512 *3.1.2.3.Sulfate attack*

513 Sulfide oxidation has been documented in concretes that contain sulfide-bearing aggregates,
514 and typically manifests as yellow discolouration accompanying a distinctive network of cracks
515 (known as map cracking) and pits/voids (known as pop-outs). These fractures critically
516 undermine the strength of the concrete, sometimes necessitating preemptive demolition of the
517 building. The onset of such damage can be rapid and appearing after as early as 3 years
518 (Rodrigues et al. 2012). In the concrete industry, this propensity for sulfate ions to react with
519 components in cement is known as sulfate attack (Müllauer et al. 2013), and the expansive
520 precipitates responsible for the fractures vary, depending on the chemistry of the aggregate and
521 cement. Importantly, sulfate attack can occur when the sulfate source is external to the concrete,
522 such as from contaminated groundwater or sewage. In cases where the source is endogenous,
523 oxidation of both pyrite and pyrrhotite have been observed (Schmidt et al. 2011). In response
524 to the recognition of this phenomenon, regulations have been introduced that specify the
525 maximum abundance of sulfide in concrete aggregates. These differ by country, but most agree
526 that it should not exceed 1% by mass, and must exclude framboidal pyrite crystals potentially
527 present in CMWGs in problematic quantity (see section 4.2.2).

528

529 *3.1.2.4.Chloride induced corrosion of steel reinforcement*

530 Caneda-Martínez et al. (2019) studied how the presence of activated coal mine waste (ACMW)
531 in concrete affects the corrosion of steel related to the chloride ion concentration of the concrete
532 porewater. When a certain threshold of chloride ion content is reached, the protective layer

533 around the steel bars, created by the highly alkaline cement pore solution, is destroyed, which
534 makes them more susceptible to corrosion. A chloride-induced accelerated corrosion test was
535 conducted on steel bars embedded in four different mortar specimens: a reference sample and
536 three others with partial substitution of OPC by activated coal mining waste (substitutions of
537 10%, 20% and 50% by volume). It was concluded that the addition of ACMW to concrete
538 induces a decline in critical chloride ion content by up to 90% when compared to the reference
539 specimens (i.e., it made the steel more susceptible to corrosion). On the other hand; however,
540 it was also found that mixes with CMWGs had a longer corrosion onset time, due to higher
541 resistance to chloride ion penetration and lower chloride diffusion coefficients, most likely
542 promoted by the pozzolanic activity of the CMWGs (see section 3.1.1).

543

544 3.1.3. Required chemical properties of CMWGs to be used as raw materials in 545 construction industry

546 Because of the aforementioned deleterious processes, the European standard EN 1744 prevents
547 the use of reactive aggregates, as per alkali silica reaction, complying with expansion limits
548 measured according to a suitable accelerated test. The same standard also limits the chloride
549 content of aggregates to 0.03% by mass and that of sulfates to 0.2% and 0.8% for coarse and
550 fine fractions respectively. The total content of sulfur, which may also be present into other
551 compounds, shall not exceed 1% by mass of aggregates (2% for blast furnace slags).

552 Presence of other substances, especially organic, which may affect the setting time of the
553 concrete is limited to amounts which would not increase the setting time by more than 120
554 minutes and would not cause a reduction of the compressive strength at 28 days by more than
555 20%.

556 4. Relationship between mineralogical and geotechnical properties of
557 CMWGs and the required characteristics as recycled aggregates.

558

559 4.1. Required physical and mechanical properties of CMWGs to be
560 used as secondary raw constituents in construction materials

561 According to the European standard EN12620:2002+A1:2008 aggregates are the granular
562 materials used in concrete batching and may be natural, manufactured or recycled. Recycled
563 aggregates are classified according to their origins into concrete and concrete products,
564 including concrete masonry units; unbound and hydraulically bound aggregates; masonry units
565 made of clay, calcium silicate or aerated concrete blocks; bituminous materials; glass; floating
566 material and miscellaneous, including metals, non-floating woods, rubber and plastic and soils.
567 Depending on their origin, the maximum percentages of constituents in the recycled aggregate
568 fractions are defined.

569 Determination of geometrical properties of aggregates is governed by EN 933 standards
570 (including 11 different parts). Besides the grain size distribution that is necessary to sort the
571 aggregates in concrete according to the best grading curve, for the use of CMWGs as aggregates
572 in concrete and construction industry the following properties are of interest:

- 573 - the flakiness index (FI), defined as the percentage, by weight, of particles in an aggregate
574 which have their average least dimension (thickness) less than 0.6 times their average
575 dimension;
- 576 - and the shape index (SI), defined as the percentage, in mass, of the non-cubic particles
577 present in the test portion are also defined to be met by any material to be used as
578 aggregates.

579 Determination of physical and mechanical properties of aggregates is on its hand governed by
 580 EN 1097 standards (10 parts). Compressive strength and resistance to wear and fragmentation
 581 are the most relevant mechanical properties to be measured, whereas for the physical ones,
 582 bulk and grain density and water absorption are of paramount interest, the latter being
 583 correlated also to freeze and thaw resistance of the aggregates and hence of the concrete as
 584 well.

585 There are fundamental reasons for the standards' requirements on the physical and mechanical
 586 properties of CMWGs to be used as secondary raw constituents in construction materials.
 587 Sections 4.2 and 4.3 present an updated review of studies on these rationales at the scales of
 588 intact coal mining aggregates and assemblies of coal mining aggregates.

589

590 4.2. Mineralogical and index properties of CMWGs

591 4.2.1. Influence of coal content on the specific gravity (G_s) of CMWGs

592 The percentage of coal in a CMWG deposit is influential to many of its properties, including
 593 specific gravity (G_s). The G_s of coal is reportedly between 1.27-1.47 (Nebel 1916; Skarżyńska
 594 1995a). Depending on the amount and the type of geomaterials co-existing with coal in the
 595 CMWGs, G_s of aggregate waste is estimated to be in the range of 2.3-2.5 (Skarżyńska 1995a),
 596 and G_s of washery waste is smaller, at 1.75-2.15 (Leventhal and de Ambrosis 1985), reflecting
 597 the additional coal extracted by the washery process. Following the general definition of G_s
 598 (Kirby 1980), it can be shown that

$$599 \quad G_{sCMWG} = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{G_{scoal}} - \frac{1}{G_{sothers}}\right)m_{coal} + \frac{1}{G_{sothers}}} \quad (3)$$

600 where m_{coal} is the percentage of coal in mining wastes by dry mass. This relationship is plotted
 601 on Figure 5 assuming $G_{sothers} = 2.65$ together with data of Kirby (1980) and Yasser et al.

602 (2004). Also plotted in Figure 5 are data from this study for samples obtained from 6 Polish
 603 mine sites. The G_s of a CMWG could be determined more easily than its carbon content in the
 604 laboratory. A drying oven, a volume measuring device and a balance are sufficient to determine
 605 G_s to a reasonable accuracy (± 1 decimal point). Knowing the G_s of a CMWG, Figure 5 could
 606 be used to approximate the corresponding carbon content of the CMWG.

607

608

Figure 5: G_s of CMWGs correlated with their carbon content

609

610 4.2.2. Influence of expandable minerals on the durability of CMWGs and 611 construction products containing CMWGs

612 The physical weathering of CMWGs is mainly driven by the presence of expandable minerals,
 613 in particular, montmorillonite and pyrite in their composition (Taylor 1974a; Taylor and Spears
 614 1970). The expansion is greatest when sodium is present as interlayer cation (Mielenz and King
 615 1952). Taylor (1974a) cited the example of a mudstone in the UK (i.e., Stafford tonstein)

616 containing a high percentage of mica-montmorillonite and exchangeable Na⁺ that it
617 disintegrates quickly and even completely when immersed in water. The primary mechanism
618 that causes this type of disintegration is by way of air breakage or slaking (Terzaghi and Peck
619 1948). When initially-dried argillaceous rocks are wetted, water gradually fills void spaces and
620 drives an increase in pore air pressure according to Boyle's law. The inflated pore air pressure
621 causes the argillaceous rocks to fail along their plane of weakness, which for most sedimentary
622 rocks, would be their bedding plane (Nezhad et al. 2018; Bagheri and Rezanian 2021). Also,
623 when rocks mined at depth are subsequently dumped in spoil heaps, the changeover from a
624 high to low effective confining stress regime induces a volumetric dilation and accelerate their
625 degradation. Another mechanism is due to a changeover from one environment to another, e.g.,
626 CMWGs originated from a saline environment when placed in contact with fresh water would
627 be subjected to significant osmotic swelling pressure (Seedsman 1986).

628 When aggregates used in concrete contain significant amount of expandable minerals, there
629 were many reports of subsequent deleterious volume change during wetting-drying cycles
630 (Knight 1949; Rhoades and Mielenz 1948). Cemented soils with significant amount of
631 expandable minerals were commonly observed to have major cracks attributed to drying-
632 wetting cycles rather than external loads (Croft 1967). Byrd (1980) reported that the Canterbury
633 bypass in the UK was constructed using CMWGs in sub-base layer but following a period of
634 heavy rainfall, serious moisture swelling was observed at construction joints. Thomas et al.
635 (1989) reported the results of a site investigation for three failed pavements in the UK. The
636 pavements were built with cemented-stabilised CMWGs which apparently met the strength and
637 durability requirements at the time of construction. Cored samples were collected from the
638 three sites and subjected to a range of tests in the laboratory (i.e., compressive strength test,
639 total-, pyritic- and sulphate-sulphur content test, X-ray diffraction, thin section examination,
640 and scanning electron microscopy examination). They concluded that oxidation of pyrite

641 mineral in the CMWGs had caused expansion of the cement-stabilised CMWGs and may have
 642 caused and/or exacerbated cracks in the pavements rendering them unserviceable.
 643 Taylor and Spears (1970) divided clay and clay-associated minerals into three groups, a similar
 644 division was adopted: kaolinites and minor chlorite, illite and muscovite, and expandables
 645 (montmorillonite, vermiculite, mix-layers, pyrite, calcite). The compositions of those minerals
 646 in some CMWGs reported in more recent literature are shown on Figure 6. Also plotted is data
 647 from this study related to the FSB mine in Spain.

648
 649 **Figure 6:** Composition of clay minerals in some CMWGs reported in the literature

650
 651 Attempts have been made to quantify the propensity of argillaceous rocks to slake using
 652 mechanical tests. Among them, Franklin and Chandra (1972) developed the slake durability
 653 test to evaluate the potential of shales, mudstones, siltstones and other clay-bearing rocks to

654 resist the weakening and disintegration resulting from drying-wetting cycles. In essence, a mass
655 of dried rock is rotated inside a perforated drum half-immersed in a water bath at 20°C for 10
656 minutes. A slake durability index I_d is calculated as the percentage ratio of the final to initial
657 dry weights of the rock in the drum i.e., the higher I_d is, the more durable it is. The test has
658 been standardised (ASTM D4644-04 (2004), ISRM (1979)) where two drying-wetting cycles
659 are specified and the slake durability index of the second cycle $I_{d(2)}$ is reported.

660 Adaptations to the slake durability test have been made, given the wide variety of mineral
661 compositions and environments argillaceous rocks are exposed to. Gökçeüglü et al. (2000)
662 collected 141 samples of weak and clay-bearing rocks from different parts of Turkey and
663 subjected them to four drying-wetting cycles of slake durability tests, XRD and uniaxial
664 compression tests. They found that the durability of clay-bearing rocks correlates best with the
665 amount of expandable clay minerals. They conducted a statistical analysis to show that strength
666 probably has no influence on the durability of laminated marls (there might be an association).

667 Mišćević and Vlastelica (2011) conducted the cycle slake durability test to characterize marls
668 from Dalmatia in Croatia. They adopted four drying-wetting cycles because they argued that
669 by the end of the 2nd cycle, although many lumps of marl did not pass through the openings of
670 the drum, the rock itself had practically disintegrated. They performed accompanying strength
671 tests and concluded that strength probably has no influence on the durability of the marls. In
672 another notable study, Vallejo (2011) conducted point load tests, slake durability tests and thin
673 section examinations of 68 shale samples from the Appalachian region of the United States.
674 They found that pore micro-geometry has a major influence on the degradation of the shales,
675 in that the air breakage mechanism was more effective in causing the slaking of those shales
676 with smooth pore boundaries than those with rough pore boundaries. Qi et al. (2015) conducted
677 a static slake durability test involving 10 wetting-drying cycles on a red mudstone taken from
678 a depth of 154.10–162.05 m in a coal mine in Shandong (China). They found that as the slaking

679 progresses, the number and size of pores and fractures increase, the structure of the surface of
680 the slaked particles becomes more disordered and complex. They also reported that when the
681 particle size of the stone is reduced by slaking to below 5 mm, it becomes more durable.
682 Some durability testing has also been conducted on stabilised geomaterials. Surendra et al.
683 (1981) studied how additives might be added to nondurable shales to improve its performance
684 during their placement and service as an embankment using the slake durability test. They
685 reported that adding lime (up to 7% of a rock's dry mass) to Osgood shale showed little
686 improvement while adding it to New Providence shale showed a substantial improvement. The
687 shales themselves were similarly nondurable but contained very different exchangeable
688 solution percentages. Kettle (1983) conducted laboratory and field trials on 10 CMWGs
689 collected from major coal fields in the UK. The CMWG samples were screened for their
690 compliance with UK requirements at the time (Department of Transport 1977), among which
691 were $LL < 45\%$ and $PL < 20\%$ and the coefficient of uniformity $C_u < 5$. They were either untreated
692 (in which case, they were prepared as samples and tested immediately) or stabilised with
693 cement at 5%, 10% of their dry mass, cured for 7 days at 20°C and atmospheric confining
694 pressure, then subjected to a range of strength tests, frost heave test (Croney and Jacobs 1970)
695 and immersion test (BS1924 1975). It was found that some CMWGs could be cement-stabilised
696 to function satisfactorily as road subbase and base materials. However, frost heave and
697 immersion tests showed that those CMWGs with significant fines (>30% finer than 75 µm)
698 were not sufficiently durable. Stavridakis and Hatzigogos (1999) created clayey admixtures in
699 the laboratory containing between 0% and 45% montmorillonite (in terms of dry mass), the
700 others being sand and kaolinite. They stabilised the mix with 4% and 12% cement then
701 conducted standard slake durability tests on the hydrated material. They found that the
702 admixtures with a liquid limit of 40% can be treated satisfactorily with 4% cement (in that it is
703 sufficiently durable for its purpose). Although the admixtures with a liquid limit of 60% can

704 be stabilised satisfactorily with 12% cement but that was considered uneconomical. In a recent
705 study, Liu et al. (2020) conducted three wetting-drying cycles slake durability tests on a paste
706 backfill comprising cement, fly ash and sand mixed according to a recipe. Their results showed
707 that a lower hydraulic conductivity contributed to a more durable paste back fill material. Their
708 microscopic analysis showed that the durability of the material might be linked to a non-
709 uniformly distributed pore structures although the mechanisms for this remain unexplored.

710

711 4.2.3. Influence of clay minerals on the plasticity of CMWGs and construction 712 products containing them

713 The plasticity of geomaterials can be attributed to the presence of clay minerals in their make-
714 up (Rezania et al. 2020). The liquid limit (LL) and plastic limit (PL) are the water content at
715 which a CMWG starts to flow like a liquid and the water content at which a CMWG transits
716 from brittle to plastic deformation, respectively. LL is determined by Casagrande's percussion
717 method or the fall cone method, and PL by the rolling thread method. The plasticity index, I_p ,
718 is determined as LL-PL. The mechanisms that enable brittle failure in the plastic limit test are
719 by air entry or cavitation (Bagheri et al. 2018; Haigh et al. 2013; Sivakumar et al. 2009;
720 Vardanega and Haigh 2014), and the governing factors are complex: mineralogy, structure,
721 texture, etc., with mineralogy playing a key role (Fleureau et al. 2002; Williams et al. 1983).
722 The presence of even a small amount of clay minerals can impact engineering behaviors of a
723 geomaterial significantly, thus LL and PL feature in the unified soil classification system for
724 classifying fine-grained geomaterials, and coarse-grained geomaterials with significant fines.
725 CMWGs may be sorted into different sizes when used as aggregates in construction products.
726 The suitability of fine-grained CMWGs as recycled materials is strongly dependent on their
727 clay minerals. The LL and PL of some CMWGs reported in the literature are listed in Table 2.

728 Also included in the table are data from this study related to coal heap samples obtained from
 729 the Forjas Santa Barbara mine in Spain.

730

731 **Table 2:** LL, PL, I_p of some weathered aggregates and washery wastes. The letters C, G, L, M,
 732 H, S, W stand for clay, gravel, low plasticity (for silt) or lean (for clay), silt, high plasticity,
 733 sand, well-graded, respectively, in the unified soil classification system.

Unified soil classification system/Gs	LL	PL	I_p	Location	Reference
GM/2.65	42	25	17	Jerada, Morocco	(Amrani et al. 2020)
GW-GC/(not available)	34.1	22	12.1	Queensland, Australia	(Gallage et al. 2015)
GW-GC/1.85	37.1	26.3	10.8	Enugu, Nigeria	(Okogbue and Ezeajugh 1991)
GW-GM/(2.53-2.75)	21.1	non-plastic	non-plastic	Matallana de Toríno, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
GM/(2.23-2.76)	19.9	non-plastic	non-plastic	Matallana de Toríno, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
GM/(2.27-2.76)	22.4	14.9	7.5	Llombera, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
GW-GM/(2.55-2.74)	17.1	14.5	2.6	Santa Lucía, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
GM/(not available)	18.8	non-plastic	non-plastic	Cinëra, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
GW-GM/(not available)	23.3	19.7	3.6	La Robla, Spain	(Cadierno et al. 2014)
CL/2.72	38	20	18	Indiana, USA	(Jung and Santagata 2014)
SM/2.59	31.5	24.0	7.5	Forjas Santa Barbara mine, Spain	This study
SW/2.13	27.2	17.7	9.5	Wollongong, Australia	(Rujikiatkamjorn et al. 2013)
GM-MH/(not available)	40-73	30-54	10-19	Eskihisar strip coal mine, Turkey	(Ulusay et al. 1995)
ML/1.61	41.7	33	7.7	Site no. WDH-1, USA	(Busch et al. 1975)
ML/1.60	38	35.3	2.7	Site no. WDH-2, USA	(Busch et al. 1975)
ML/1.58	34.3	non-plastic	non-plastic	Site no. BDH-1, USA	(Busch et al. 1975)
MH/1.87	51.1	38	13.1	Site no. BDH-2, USA	(Busch et al. 1975)
CL/2.59	32.3	13.6	18.7	Dinajpur, Bangladesh	(Hossain et al. 2018)
CL/2.63	26.9	17.1	9.8	Basundhara opencast coal mine, India	(Mallick and Mishra 2017)

734

735 The data from Table 2 are plotted on Casagrande's plasticity chart overlaid with locations of
736 common clay minerals in Figure 7. Casagrande (1948) suggested this plot as an approximate
737 way to identify the dominant mineral groups present in soils (Holtz and Kovacs 1981). Data
738 from Table 2 are shown to plot primarily on the lower left corner of the chart, indicative of
739 materials that do not hold water well and exhibit non-plastic to moderately plastic behaviours.
740 Mineralogical analysis of the lean clay (CL) from Dinajpur (Bangladesh) was not reported by
741 Hossain et al. (2018) but the California bearing ratio test results showed that it has an expansion
742 ratio of 1.51 thus was unsuitable to be recycled in a road subgrade. X-ray diffraction (XRD)
743 analysis of the sample from the FSB mine in Spain shows that the clay minerals in it comprise
744 of 20% illite and 10% kaolinite, which are non-expandable, and 5% vermiculite which has
745 limited expansion capacity.

746

747

Figure 7: CMWGs' plasticity and clay minerals indicated on Casagrande's chart

748 4.2.4. Grain size and shape, and grain size distribution (GSD) of CMWGs

749 The shape of individual granular particles (with particle sizes $> 63 \mu\text{m}$) is at least as important
750 as the grain size distribution in governing their engineering response (Holtz and Kovacs 1981).
751 Many measures of shape exist, at the most basic level of description, and a useful distinction
752 can be made here between needlelike/flaky particles and bulky particles (Holtz and Kovacs
753 1981; Rodriguez et al. 2012). The percentage of flaky particles in a given soil tends to increase
754 with decreasing grain size as a consequence of the geological processes of soil formation
755 (Terzaghi and Peck 1948). When being compressed, needlelike/flaky particles compact more
756 than bulky particles (Holtz and Kovacs 1981; Penman 1971); and when being sheared, their
757 different shapes contribute differently to frictional resistance (Holtz and Kovacs 1981;
758 Terzaghi and Peck 1948). In particular, particle shapes strongly affect how materials can be
759 mixed and compacted. As particles become less bulky, both the maximum void ratio e_{max} and
760 minimum void ratio e_{min} increase, and $e_{\text{max}}-e_{\text{min}}$ also increases (Cho et al. 2006; Cubrinovski
761 and Ishihara 2002; Fraser 1935; Santamarina and Cho 2005). In terms of size and grading, it
762 has been found that when two or more granular soil samples of the same mineralogical content
763 are compacted to the same density under the same effective confining stress, as D_{50} (grain size
764 for 50% finer by weight on a GSD plot) increases, the peak shear strength and volumetric
765 dilatancy decrease; and for soils with the same D_{50} , a less uniform grading (i.e., higher
766 coefficient of uniformity C_u) yields a slightly lower peak shear strength (Harehdasht et al. 2018;
767 Kirkpatrick 1965). However, when sheared to constant volume condition, the shear strength of
768 granular soils depend primarily on the mineral compositions of the particles (Muir Wood 1990;
769 Negussey et al. 1988).

770 The ways coal-bearing rocks are mechanically broken and mined, and the treatment of left-
771 overs are consequential to properties of CMWGs. This can be reflected on a grain size
772 distribution (GSD) plot. The GSDs of many geomaterials show a self-similar (fractal)

773 distribution (Perfect and Kay 1995). Researchers demonstrated that the breaking up of larger
 774 clusters/particles by mechanical actions results in smaller clusters/particles, the resulting GSD
 775 exhibits fractal characteristic (Coop et al. 2004; McDowell et al. 1996). Tang et al. (2014)
 776 conducted sieving experiments on 30 kg samples of coal gangues and found that their GSDs
 777 exhibit fractal characteristics. Yang et al. (2021) conducted drop weight tests of coal samples
 778 and found that the GSDs of broken fragments exhibit fractal characteristics. Ding and Liu
 779 (2021) immersed a soft slate in water for different durations and found that it disintegrates into
 780 particles with GSDs obeying different fractal distributions. Latest studies show that the GSDs
 781 of many mine tailings (Qiu and Seg0 2001; Vo et al. 2020) and coal tailings (Islam 2021; Salam
 782 et al. 2019; Vidler et al. 2020) also exhibit fractal characteristics. Russell (2010) described a
 783 GSD exhibiting a single fractal scaling as:

$$784 \quad \%M_s(L < d_s) = 100 \left(\frac{d_s^{3-D_s} - d_{s \min}^{3-D_s}}{d_{s \max}^{3-D_s} - d_{s \min}^{3-D_s}} \right) \quad (4)$$

785 where D_s , d_s , $d_{s \max}$, $d_{s \min}$, M_s denote, respectively, fractal dimension of a GSD, a specific grain
 786 size, the maximum grain size, the minimum grain size, and dry mass of particles.

787 GSDs of some coal aggregates and tailings reported in the literature are replotted in Figure 8
 788 to show how they could be approximated by Eq. (4). Figure 8 shows that a well-graded GSD
 789 curve corresponds to a higher D_s and a poorly-graded GSD curve corresponds to a lower D_s .
 790 Also plotted in the figure is this study's data obtained from the FSB mine in Spain. The GSD
 791 of this sample obeys a single fractal scaling law with $D_s \approx 2.63$.

792 Eq. (4) may be extended to describe a GSD exhibiting double fractal characteristics as:

$$793 \quad \%M_s(L < d_s) = \frac{M_1}{M_1+M_2} 100 \left(\frac{d_s^{3-D_{s1}} - d_{s \min 1}^{3-D_{s1}}}{d_{s \max 1}^{3-D_{s1}} - d_{s \min 1}^{3-D_{s1}}} \right) + \frac{M_2}{M_1+M_2} 100 \left(\frac{d_s^{3-D_{s2}} - d_{s \min 2}^{3-D_{s2}}}{d_{s \max 2}^{3-D_{s2}} - d_{s \min 2}^{3-D_{s2}}} \right) \quad (5)$$

794 where M_1 is the mass percentage of population 1 (fractal dimension D_{s1}), M_2 is the mass
 795 percentage of population 2 (fractal dimension D_{s2}), and $d_{s \min 1} < d_{s \max 1}$, $d_{s \min 2} < d_{s \max 2}$. D_{s1} can

796 be approximated on a GSD plot but D_{s2} would need to be identified by upscaling its mass
 797 percentage to 100%. Figure 8 shows how D_{s1} may be approximated from the GSDs of samples
 798 exhibiting double fractal characteristics. The samples of Yu et al. (2019) and Qiu and Segó
 799 (2001) with GSDs on this figure were collected *in situ* from an Appalachian coalfield in
 800 Kentuckys (USA) and from a coal wash plant in the Coal Valley mine in Alberta (Canada),
 801 respectively.

802

803

804

Figure 8: Fractality and heterogeneity in GSDs of CMWGs

805

806 Knowing the GSD is useful for estimating the mass and volume of aggregates needed to make
 807 CMWG-bearing construction products. This can be made even simpler when the GSD obeys a
 808 single or double fractal scaling law. However, there is a high degree of heterogeneity within
 809 the CWMGs in spoil heaps. Coal mining wastes weather rapidly when exposed to the elements

810 (Bishop 1973; Skarżyńska 1995a) but may remain relatively intact when buried deeply within
811 an unburnt spoil heap (Taylor 1975), thus depending on various factors (e.g., how the original
812 wastes were processed and deposited, how long they have been left there, whether they were
813 disturbed during storage) the GSDs of CMWGs reclaimed from storage may eventually be
814 more complex.

815

816 4.3. Mineralogical and state-dependant properties of CMWGs

817 4.3.1. Water retention and hydraulic conductivity of CMWGs

818 The saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s) of intact coal mining waste aggregates varies
819 depending on the K_s of their parenting rocks; e.g. approximately 10^{-4} - 10^{-8} cm/s for sandstone,
820 10^{-7} - 10^{-11} cm/s for shale, and smaller for unfractured metamorphic and igneous rocks (Bear
821 1972; Freeze and Cherry 1979). The very low K_s of intact coal mining waste aggregates can
822 be attributed to their small pore sizes, i.e. generally smaller than 50 nm (Mastalerz et al. 2012;
823 Ma et al. 2017; Li et al. 2019). However, when coal mining waste geomaterials are deposited
824 in spoil heaps or impoundment facilities (as CMWGs), or processed into construction products,
825 it also becomes relevant to consider K_s of an aggregation of coal mining particles (in addition
826 to K_s of intact aggregates themselves). The K_s of CMWGs is dependent on their grain and pore
827 size distributions, and compactness (Holubec 1976; Leventhal and de Ambrosis 1985;
828 Skarżyńska 1995a; Ulusay et al. 1995). The value of K_s for CMWGs vary widely because these
829 geomaterials are susceptible to rapid weathering (Bishop 1973; Cobb 1977; Holubec 1976;
830 Saxena et al. 1984; Skarżyńska 1995a; Taylor and Spears 1973) and fabric inhomegenity (Cobb
831 1977; Kirby 1980; Saxena et al. 1984). An increase in the degree of weathering is associated
832 with an increase in the portion of finer particles and pores and a decrease in K_s . Freshly wrought
833 coal waste aggregates deposited loosely in spoil heaps can be very permeable with $K_s=10^{-1}$ - 10^{-
834 $2}$ cm/s (Skarżyńska 1995a), but with weathering and different levels of compaction, K_s can be

835 anywhere between 10^{-1} to 10^{-8} cm/s for coal waste aggregates (Holubec 1976). Entrainment of
836 fines at the interface between a tailing lagoon and its embankment may reduce K_s down to 10^{-}
837 12 cm/s, i.e., effectively impermeable.

838 It was found that K_s of CMWGs measured *in situ* in the UK are about two orders of magnitude
839 higher than those measured in the laboratory (Cobb 1977; Kirby 1980). Hence the UK-based
840 studies recommend a greater reliance on *in situ* measurements (Murray and Symons 1974;
841 National Coal Board 1972). Saxena et al. (1984) found the average K_s measured *in situ* (on a
842 site in the USA) to be somewhat higher than in the laboratory and attributed this difference to
843 fabric. They found that with decreasing lift thickness, the field permeability decreases.
844 Rujikiatkamjorn et al. (2013) found that compacting the coal wash at wet and dry sides of the
845 optimum moisture content results in samples with different fabrics, and K_s versus void ratio
846 relations. For coal tailing deposits, distinct layers of different physical compositions are often
847 noticeable on visual examination.

848 With the exception of those wastes buried below ground water level to manage the AMD
849 problem, CMWGs *in situ* are generally unsaturated. Recent studies (Alonso and Cardoso 2010;
850 Oldecop and Rodari 2017; William 2012) showed a wide scope of applications of
851 geomechanics of unsaturated media in coal mining and post-mining operations. Geomechanics
852 of unsaturated media can be applied to characterise behaviors of CMWGs and porous
853 construction products containing them. In particular, water retention curve and hydraulic
854 conductivity function could be obtained to quantify how fluids and gases move through the
855 pore spaces. To show this simply, the 1D steady state version of Darcy's law (Buckingham
856 1907; Griffiths and Lu 2005; Richard and Fireman 1941) can be expressed as:

$$857 \quad q = -K \left(\frac{d\psi}{dz} + 1 \right) \quad (6)$$

858 where q is the flow rate (cm/s) and $d\psi/dz$ is the pressure gradient driving flow in the z direction.
859 Assuming $\psi = u_a - u_w = s$ (kPa) where u_a , u_w , $s \equiv$ pore air pressure, pore water pressure and matric
860 suction, respectively, then i) the water retention curve is $s = f(s_e, S_r, e, \text{etc.})$ where $s_e \equiv$ air
861 entry/expulsion suction, $S_r \equiv$ degree of saturation, $e \equiv$ void ratio, and ii) the unsaturated
862 hydraulic conductivity function is $K = f(K_s, S_r, e, \text{etc.})$. There are many empirical models of
863 water retention curve and hydraulic conductivity function in the literature, adopting them often
864 requires calibration against relevant experimental data.

865 Water movements induce volumetric changes in intact coal mining aggregates, a behaviour
866 found to be strongly dependant on coal rank and pore characteristics (Suuberg et al. 1993;
867 Stanmore et al. 1997; McCutcheon et al. 2001; Ma et al. 2016). However, there are limited
868 experimental studies on water retention characteristics of aggregations of coal waste particles
869 (as CMWGs). Sharma et al. (1993) mixed lumps of coal and soil together in different ratios to
870 create coal spoil samples then tested them in a pressure plate device. They reported different
871 water retention behaviours between samples containing commercial lignite (with high water
872 repellency) and samples containing degraded lignite (with low water repellency). Qiu and Sego
873 (2001) studied the water retention characteristics of a coal tailing using the pressure plate test.
874 The air entry value was reported to be 18 kPa which is somewhat low considering that the
875 material was classified as a low plasticity clay. Residual volumetric water content was 18%
876 which is rather high. Fityus and Li (2006) conducted filter paper tests of processed Australian
877 coals and reported a significant difference between the soil water retention curve of the coals
878 and of a typical soil due to the coals' strong hydrophobic nature. They concluded that on drying
879 from a saturated state, processed coal would have negligible suction until $S_r < 0.5-0.6$, hence
880 much of the moisture in stockpiled coal would not contribute to forming films and adhesion to
881 suppress the release of dust. Vidler et al. (2020) obtained the soil water retention curves of a
882 coal tailing, the mineral fraction and the coal fraction using a tensiometer and a dewpoint

883 potentiometer. They found that the presence of coal in the tailing has a significant impact on
 884 the water retention behaviour of the coal tailing. The coal fraction desaturates at low suction
 885 on drying from a fully wetted state, its inclusion in tailing might cause localized
 886 hydrophobicity, and overall lower the air entry value of the geomaterial. Liu et al. (2021)
 887 investigated in experiments the effect of drying-wetting cycles on the hydromechanical
 888 behaviour of a compacted coal gangue. They found the pore-size distribution curve of a coal
 889 gangue to exhibit a bimodal feature. Both the inter-aggregate pores and intra-aggregate pore
 890 volumes were found to be affected by hydraulic loading.

891

892 4.3.2. Shear strength of CMWGs

893 As it is customary and widely adopted in practical geomechanics field, Mohr-Coulomb
 894 parameters are adopted here to discuss the shear strength of CMWGs. The shear strength
 895 parameter τ can be defined in terms of total and effective stresses as:

$$896 \quad \tau = c + \sigma \tan \varphi \quad (7)$$

$$897 \quad \tau = c' + \sigma' \tan \varphi' \quad (8)$$

898 where $c, \sigma, \varphi, c', \sigma', \varphi'$ denote total cohesion, total stress, total friction angle, effective cohesion,
 899 effective stress, effective friction angle, respectively. The effective stress (σ') for saturated and
 900 unsaturated CMWGs can be defined respectively as (Bishop 1959; Terzaghi 1943):

$$901 \quad \sigma' = \sigma - u_w \quad (8)$$

$$902 \quad \sigma' = (\sigma - u_a) + \chi(u_a - u_w) \quad (9)$$

903 where $\chi \equiv$ effective stress parameter ($\chi=1$ for fully saturated conditions and $\chi=0$ for fully dry
 904 conditions). For unsaturated geomaterial, $u_a - u_w = s$. The $\chi(u_a - u_w)$ component in Eq. (9)
 905 contributes to the effective stress and shear strength of unsaturated geomaterials. Bishop (1960)

906 suggested that χ depends on many factors including S_r , s , the drying-wetting cycle and the
 907 stress history of the geomaterial. Characterising the dependency of $\chi(u_a-u_w)$ to different states
 908 is the key to estimate the shear strength of unsaturated geomaterials.

909 Different types of shearing tests and interpretations of test data contributed to a large variation
 910 of c' , ϕ' for CMWGs reported in the literature (Holubec 1976). This section will focus on
 911 triaxial shearing tests.

912 The shear strength of saturated CMWGs has been extensively characterized in triaxial shearing
 913 tests. Typical c' , ϕ' of CMWGs obtained from consolidated undrained (CU), consolidated
 914 drained (CD), multistage consolidated undrained (m-CU), multistage consolidated drained (m-
 915 CD) tests reported in the literature are shown in Table 3. Also included, is this study's data of
 916 a coal heap sample obtained from the FSB mine (Spain). The shear strength of a CMWG varies
 917 considerably depending on its sampling location (Bishop et al. 1969; Kirby 1980). The c' , ϕ' in
 918 Table 3 were the peak shear strength parameters for the level of shear strain, compactedness
 919 and effective confining stress considered in those studies. The c' , ϕ' in Table 3 do not differ
 920 significantly between coal tailing and coal waste aggregates. The shear strength of coal tailing
 921 in Appalachian region, USA was found to be relatively high given its grain size distribution
 922 (Holubec 1976). Thompson et al. (1973) and Taylor (1974b) attributed the relatively high shear
 923 strength of coal tailing to the presence of the coal mineral in it. Kirby (1980) found that both
 924 the coal content and shear strength of coal tailings in the UK were in fact higher than those of
 925 the coal waste aggregates.

926 **Table 3.** (c' , ϕ') obtained from consolidated undrained (CU), consolidated drained (CD),
 927 multistage consolidated undrained (m-CU), multistage consolidated drained (m-CU) tests on
 928 saturated samples

Type	Unified Soil Classification System/Gs	c' (kPa)	ϕ' (°)	Test	Location	Reference
Impounded waste	(not available)/1.75-2.22	0	22-39	CD	Aberfan, UK	(Thompson and Rodin 1972)

Impounded waste	(not available)/1.61-2.01	0-20	25-42.7	CU	Peckfield, UK	(Kirby 1980)
Impounded waste	(not available)/1.42-2.32	0-7	30.5-35	CU	East Hetton Colliery, UK	(Kirby 1980)
Impounded waste	(not available)/1.42-2.32	0-27	31.8-40.5	CU	Maltby, UK	(Kirby 1980)
Impounded waste	CL/1.94	10	32	CU	Coal Valley Mine, Canada	(Qiu and Seg0 2001)
Impounded waste	(not available)/1.34-1.66	0-14.34	32-40	CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Holubec 1976)
Impounded waste	SM/2.10	13.8	29	m-CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Impounded waste	ML/2.10	25.5	26	m-CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Impounded waste	ML/2.10	24.8	30	m-CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Impounded waste	SM/2.10	20.7	31	m-CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Impounded waste	SM/2.20	16.5	36	m-CD	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Impounded waste	ML/2.20	13.1	38	m-CD	Appalachian Region, USA	(Salam et al. 2019)
Coal waste aggregate	(not available)/1.80-2.70	0	23-42	CD	Aberfan, UK	(Thompson and Rodin 1972)
Coal waste aggregate	(not available)/1.75-2.50	0-24	28-41	CU	Appalachian Region, USA	(Holubec 1976)
Coal waste aggregate	GM-MH/(not available)	0-10	23-35	CD	Eskihisar coal mine, Turkey	(Ulusay et al. 1995)
Coal waste aggregate	GW-GC/(not available)	1-40	33.2-38.6	m-CU	Queensland, Australia	(Gallage et al. 2015)
Coal waste aggregate	SC/2.23	0	35	CD	NSW, Australia	(Heitor et al. 2016)
Coal waste aggregate	(not available)/(not available)	5-25	33-36	CD	QLD, NSW & VIC, Australia	(Simmons 2020)
Coal waste aggregate	SM/2.59	0	29.1	CU	Forjas Santa Barbara mine, Spain	This study

929

930 There are few laboratory experiments investigating the effective shear strength parameters (c' ,
931 ϕ') of unsaturated CMWGs. Most experiments conducted on unsaturated coal mining wastes
932 obtained the total strength parameters (c , ϕ). Eqs. (7)-(9) show that the separate impact of u_a ,
933 u_w and χ on shear strength cannot be distinguished using the total strength parameters c , ϕ .

934 Saxena et al. (1984) reported that the unconfined compression strength of CMWGs was more
935 dependent on the water content at the time of testing rather than on dry density. Okogbue and
936 Ezeajugh (1991) investigated an unsaturated Nigerian coal waste in experiments and obtained
937 $\phi=13.4^{\circ}$ - 15° and $c=55$ - 57 kPa in UU (unconsolidated undrained) test, and $c=38.6$ - 39.2 kPa in
938 UC (unconfined compression) test. The relatively high c and low ϕ were attributed to the type
939 of tests (i.e., UU, UC). If the test data for Forjas Santa Barbara mine (Spain) (Table 3) were to
940 be interpreted in total stress, $c=111$ kPa $>$ $c'=0$ kPa, $\phi=27.7^{\circ}$ $<$ $\phi'=29.1^{\circ}$. Indraratna et al. (1994)
941 showed that ϕ of compacted coal tailings obtained from unsaturated CU tests was maximum at
942 optimum moisture content although the influence of void ratio was not accounted for separately
943 in their results.

944 Particle breakage is another factor that affects the shear strength of weak coal-bearing rocks
945 and aggregates and their potential for reuse. It has been established that many types of
946 aggregates when used as rockfills (including coal-bearing aggregates) are prone to particle
947 breakage once the effective confining stress reached a critical value (Marachi et al. 1972;
948 Marsal 1967, 1973). Indraratna et al. (1998) tested latite basalt aggregates (flakiness index
949 FI=25%, $D_{50}=30$ - 40 mm, $C_u=1.5$ - 1.6) in a large triaxial test to characterise their shear
950 behaviour as railway ballast. They reported a departure in shear and deformation behaviours of
951 the basalt between low effective confining stress (<100 kPa) and higher effective confining
952 stress. Breakage was found to be influenced by the shape, size, grading of particles and the
953 compactedness of test samples. At higher levels of effective confining stress, localized
954 breakage occurred at contact points between particles. The contact stress can be much higher
955 than the applied deviator stress. Broken particles fill up the void spaces and reduce the
956 hydraulic conductivity of the porous medium (Ma et al. 2017). In practice, this mechanism of
957 particle degradation is commonly observed to lead to clogging and undrained failure of railway
958 ballast (Chrismer and Read 1994). Heitor et al. (2016) tested a coal wash from Wollongong

959 (Australia) in drained and undrained triaxial compression tests in effective confining stresses
960 of up to 600 kPa, and isotropic compression tests in effective confining stresses of up to 1,400
961 kPa. It was found that the compaction of the coal wash aggregates at their natural moisture
962 content into triaxial samples induced significant particle breakage. The aggregates compacted
963 under 170, 341 and 681 kJ/m³ (using standard Proctor compaction device) each attained unique
964 effective strength parameters (c' , ϕ') at the critical state. Consolidation and shearing of the coal
965 wash also induced significant particle breakage when a critical effective confining stress (in
966 that case, 127 kPa) was exceeded.

967

968 5. Conclusions

969 There is currently a drive to develop innovative concepts for managing, recycling and
970 upcycling waste geomaterials generated by coal mining activities in Europe and throughout the
971 world. CMWGs present us with many challenging problems such as spontaneous combustion
972 and leaching of acidic water to the surrounding environment, slope instability of spoil heaps
973 and flow liquefaction of impoundment facilities. Storing CMWG deposits consume economic
974 resources yet there is great demand of raw geomaterials in the construction industry. This paper
975 reviewed the properties of CMWGs relevant to assessing their suitability as raw geomaterials
976 in construction industry, from geochemical, geotechnical and structural engineering
977 perspectives.

- 978 • With regards to geochemical aspects of CMWGs, it was emphasized previously in the
979 literature (e.g., Younger 2004) that coal mining wastes are associated with some major
980 problems such as air pollution, fire hazards, ground deformation, water pollution, and water
981 re-source depletion. Assessing the suitability of CMWGs for upcycling as a secondary raw
982 material for higher level civil engineering applications requires a robust understanding of

983 the geochemical processes it is likely to undergo. The suitability of CMWGs for a particular
984 construction application can vary from one mine to another due to their diverse mineral
985 contents. It was found in this review that CMWGs are good SCM candidates because they
986 often contain large fractions of clay minerals that can be conditioned (and blended with
987 other materials when necessary) to acquire pozzolanic properties, as has been demonstrated
988 in many recent studies (e.g., Bich et al. 2009; Frías et al. 2012; Vigil de la Villa et al. 2014;
989 García Giménez et al. 2016; Caneda-Martínez et al. 2019; Rodríguez et al. 2021). It was
990 also concluded in this review that more research is needed to investigate the propensity for
991 CMWGs to promote ASR (since this condition can take years to realise) and ACR (since
992 the extent to which this reaction impacts durability is not sufficiently delineated from other
993 processes).

994 • Previous reviews (Holubec 1976; Skarżyńska 1995a; Masoudian et al. 2019) emphasized
995 that CMWGs are chemically and physically highly-heterogeneous, and CMWGs have been
996 utilised successfully in many geotechnical and specialised structural applications
997 (Hammond 1988; Skarżyńska 1995b; Liu and Liu 2010). This review focuses on the
998 interactions between mineralogy, geotechnical indices, and state-dependant properties of
999 CMWGs. It was found that the mineral content of a CMWG can influence both the
1000 durability and the strength of its potential construction applications. Simple techniques are
1001 provided to aid the initial screening of CMWGs for their suitability. When a more
1002 substantive screening of CMWGs for suitability is needed, it was found that quantifying
1003 the amount of expandable minerals and durability performance is important. Moreover, it
1004 was found that the highly-heterogenous state-dependent properties of CMWGs (e.g., water
1005 retention, hydraulic conductivity, shear strength) are impacted by complex factors such as
1006 coal content, particle size and shape, pore scale spanning 6-9 orders of magnitude, and the
1007 presence of pore air and pore water in the interstitial void space. In this respect, recent

1008 studies (Alonso and Cardoso 2010; Oldecop and Rodari 2017; William 2012) showed that
1009 there is a wide scope of applications of geomechanics of unsaturated media in
1010 characterising the behaviors of CMWGs and porous construction products containing them.

- 1011 • There are still scattered experiences with reference to the application of CMWGs as
1012 constituents of concrete and cement based mixtures either as supplementary cementitious
1013 material replacing Ordinary Portland Cement or as recycled aggregates in substitution of
1014 natural ones. Surveyed studies have highlighted on the one hand the importance of proper
1015 mineralogical and mechanical characterization of CMWGs for their suitability to the
1016 purpose above. On the other hand, the need and possibility have been demonstrated of
1017 finding, through appropriate tests, the optimal replacement percentages in order to obtain a
1018 concrete mix featuring the level of mechanical and durability performance required for the
1019 intended engineering application. Variations, generally reductions, due to the incorporation
1020 of CMWGs can be kept within limits which still make the obtained concretes suitable for
1021 the intended purposes through appropriate selection and grading of the same CMWGs and
1022 suitable mix-design approaches, highlighting the importance and need of a unified
1023 framework for promoting their valorization into cement based construction materials and
1024 products.

1025

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1031

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